

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Acetoacetanilide and Some Other Nitrogen Donor Ligands

BIPIN B. MAHAPATRA and DEBENDRA PANDA

Department of Chemistry, G. M. College, Sambalpur-768 004

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Mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) with acetoacetanilide and some other nitrogen donor ligands of compositions $[MX(acacN)B]$, $[MX(acacN)(H_2O)_2]$, $[MX(acacN)B_2H_2O]$ and $[MX(acacN)B_3]$, where $M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$; $X = Cl^-, Br^-, NO_3^-, ClO_4^-$; $acacN =$ acetoacetanilide anion; $B =$ pyridine, γ -picoline, quinoline, have been prepared. The compounds have been characterised on the basis of analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral data. The thermal decompositions of a few cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes were studied by DTG and DTA techniques.

SYNTHESIS of metal complexes having unusual coordination numbers through a process of mixed ligation has evoked a lot of interest in recent years. Several mixed ligand pentacoordinated complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and cadmium(II) have been reported¹⁻⁶ using oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur donor ligands. It was therefore thought worthwhile to study the reactions of Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with acetoacetanilide in 1 : 1 stoichiometric proportions in the presence of nitrogen donor ligands. The present paper reports some tetra-, penta-, and hexacoordinated mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

$[Co(NO_3)(acacN)(H_2O)_2]$ and $[Cu(NO_3)(acacN)(H_2O)_2]$: The compounds of this type were prepared by reacting the ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) nitrate (2.9 g) and copper(II) nitrate (1.9 g) and acetoacetanilide (1.7 g) in hot ethanol separately followed by dropwise addition of ammonia with constant shaking.

$[MX(acacN)B_2H_2O]$: Metal salts, acetoacetanilide and the nitrogen donor ligands (1 : 1 : 2 mol) in ethanolic medium were reacted under reflux. The resulting solutions were then neutralised by adding conc. ammonia dropwise with shaking.

$[MX(acacN)B]$: These were prepared by reacting metal salts, acetoacetanilide and nitrogen donor ligands in ethanolic medium (1 : 1 : 1 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h over a water-bath. Conc. ammonia was then added

slowly dropwise to the slightly warm solution when the metal complexes separated out.

$[Co(NO_3)(acacN)Q_2]$ and $[Co(NO_3)(acacN)(\gamma-Pic)_2]$: These compounds were obtained by reacting the ethanolic solutions of cobalt(II) nitrate (2.9 g), acetoacetanilide (1.7 g) and quinoline (2.5 ml) and γ -picoline (1.9 ml) separately and refluxing the contents for nearly 1 h. Conc. ammonia was then added dropwise to the moderately hot solution when the compounds separated out.

The compounds thus isolated were filtered, washed with ethanol several times followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Metal and nitrogen contents in the complexes were estimated by the usual methods. Conductance was measured in 10^{-3} M acetone solution of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on the solid samples by the Gouy method. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in 10^{-3} M acetone solution, using Hilger and Watt Uvispeck spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analyses were carried out by the Hungarian Optical Works, Hungary, in the ambient temperature of the furnace with a heating rate of 10°min^{-1} . Analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility and ir data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Based upon the analytical and conductance data, the complexes have the following compositions $[M(NO_3)(acacN)(H_2O)_2]$, $M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II}$; $[MX(acacN)B_2H_2O]$, $M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and $X = Cl^-, NO_3^-$; $[Mx(acacN)B]$, $M = Co^{II}, Zn^{II}$ and $X =$

TABLE I

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	M. p.	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)			
					M	N	$\frac{\nu_{C-O}}{\nu_{C-N}}$	$\frac{\nu_{M-O}}{\nu_{M-N}}$
1.	CoCl LQ	Blue	235	4.6	14.75 (14.58)	7.00 (6.85)	1100 1625	450 520
2.	CoClL(γ -pic) ₂ H ₂ O	Violet	237	5.0	15.79 (15.65)	11.23 (11.08)	1105 1620	445 510
3.	CoClL(py) ₂ H ₂ O	Violet	200	5.0	13.22 (13.18)	9.41 (9.27)	1100 1620	440 515
4.	Co(NO ₃)L(H ₂ O) ₂	Pink	>280	5.1	16.80 (16.69)	8.00 (7.88)	1105 1615	445 510
5.	Co(NO ₃)L Q ₂	Leafy green	>280	4.8	10.63 (10.50)	10.09 (9.85)	1100 1620	450 515
6.	Co(NO ₃)L(γ -pic) ₂	Leafy green	>280	4.85	12.21 (12.10)	11.59 (11.46)	1100 1625	445 520
7.	Co(ClO ₄)L(γ -pic) ₂	Brown	210	5.0	9.62 (9.51)	9.13 (9.05)	1100 1620	440 515
8.	CuClL(γ -pic) ₂ H ₂ O	Blue	172	1.78	11.07 (10.90)	8.76 (8.68)	1105 1620	445 510
9.	CuClL Q ₂ H ₂ O	Blue	200	1.77	11.43 (11.35)	7.62 (7.58)	1100 1625	440 515
10.	Cu(NO ₃)L(H ₂ O) ₂	Green	>280	1.79	17.74 (17.60)	7.89 (7.78)	1105 1620	450 510
11.	Cu(NO ₃)LQ ₂ H ₂ O	Blue	215	1.78	10.91 (10.78)	9.70 (9.56)	1100 1620	445 520
12.	Cu(ClO ₄)L(γ -pic) ₂	Chocolate	140	1.78	12.00 (11.89)	8.00 (7.86)	1095 1615	445 520
13.	ZnClL(γ -pic)	White	222	-	17.61 (17.56)	7.58 (7.47)	1100 1620	440 510
14.	ZnClL Q	Brown	220	-	16.50 (16.38)	6.91 (6.76)	1105 1625	440 515
15.	ZnBrL(γ -pic)	White	140	-	15.70 (15.59)	6.76 (6.67)	1100 1615	450 510
16.	ZnBrL(py)	White	205	-	16.25 (16.18)	7.00 (6.88)	1100 1625	445 520

L = acetoacetanilide anion, γ -pic = γ -picoline, py = pyridine, Q = quinoline.

Cl⁻, Br⁻; [MX(acacN)B₂], M = Co^{II} and X = ClO₄⁻; [MX(acacN)B₂], M = Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and X = ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻; acacN = acetoacetanilide anion, B = pyridine, γ -picoline, quinoline.

The ir active bands at 1630 (C=O), 1590 (C=C) and 1150 cm⁻¹ (C-O) in acetoacetanilide moiety appear at \sim 1620, 1580 and 1100 cm⁻¹, respectively in the metal complexes. Hence it may be concluded that the ligand (acacNH) is bonded to the metal ions through both the amidic and enolic oxygen atoms. Further evidence of bonding of oxygen atom is provided by the appearance⁶ of metal-oxygen band at \sim 450 cm⁻¹ in the far ir spectra of the complexes. In case of cobalt(II) and copper(II) perchlorate complexes, two sharp bands are observed at 985 and 1100 cm⁻¹ indicative⁷ of the coordinated perchlorate group in conformity with conductance data. Strong absorption bands at \sim 1370 and 1215 cm⁻¹ suggest unidentate coordination^{8,9} of the nitrate complexes. This is also supported by the conductance data. Most of the absorption bands due to the heterocyclic bases get shifted in the mixed ligand complexes indicating their bonding to the metal ions. The sharp band observed at 3300 cm⁻¹ (NH) in the

free ligand and in the metal complexes indicates the non-coordination of the amidic nitrogen atom of acetoacetanilide molecule to the metal ions. In case of some cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes, the presence of coordinated water is ascertained by the observation^{10,11} of a broad double hump at \sim 3450 cm⁻¹ followed by the appearance of a sharp peak at \sim 840 cm⁻¹. The appearance of the bands at \sim 520 cm⁻¹ in the far ir spectra of mixed ligand complexes indicates the bonding of metal ions with different heterocyclic nitrogen atoms thereby confirming their presence in the complexes. Metal-halogen stretching frequencies however, fall beyond the range of the instrument used.

In the electronic spectra of cobalt(II) complexes (Sl. nos. 2,3,4 and 7 of Table 1), the absorption bands at \sim 8,450(11), 18,500(24) and 20,00(32) cm⁻¹ have been attributed to ⁴T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ⁴T_{2g}(F), \rightarrow ⁴A_{2g}(F) and \rightarrow ⁴T_{1g}(P) transitions, respectively in conformity with an octahedral configuration^{12,13}. This is supported by the high magnetic moment values as well⁷. In the case of cobalt(II) complexes (Sl. nos. 5 and 6) three bands are observed at \sim 19,600 (ν_1), 15,260 (ν_2) and 11,400 (ν_3) cm⁻¹ in

conformity with the earlier observation^{14,15} for pentacoordinated Co^{II} complexes. In the electronic spectrum of quinoline adduct of chloro-complex (Sl. no. 1), two bands are observed at 15,300 (1400) and 8,500 (210) cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ transitions, respectively. The high extinction coefficient value of ${}^4\text{A}_2 \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ and low μ_{eff} value (4.6 B.M.) support a tetrahedral configuration for the complex. All the copper(II) complexes except the perchlorate complex show a broad band in the 13,750–14,300 cm^{-1} region due to ${}^2\text{E}_g \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_{2g}$ transition¹² indicating a distorted octahedral stereochemistry of the complexes. A single broad band is noticed for the perchlorate complex at 15,400 cm^{-1} in conformity with the spectral band for the penta-coordinated copper(II) complexes reported¹⁶.

The thermogravimetric study of four representative compounds has been reported. The cobalt complex $[\text{Co}(\text{acacN})\text{Cl}(\gamma\text{-pic})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ starts losing its mass gradually with the rise of temperature and between 80–160°, as observed from the TGA graph, loses the water molecule with a weight loss of 3.87%. Then again it loses one molecule of γ -picoline as evident from the sharp endothermic peak at 250° on the DTA curve with a weight loss of 23.87% against the observed value 23.26%. With the rise of temperature it loses again the second molecule of γ -picoline at 340° with a loss of 43.8%. Then the compound starts losing its weight and at 600°, shown by the sharp endothermic peak, loses 1/3rd. of the acetoacetanilide molecule with a loss of 56.7% against the theoretical value 57.5%. Again it loses 1/3rd. of acetoacetanilide at 800° as evident from the sharp exothermic peak with a loss of 69.4%. Then the compound loses rest 1/3rd. of acetoacetanilide moiety along with chlorine atom with a loss of 86.3% weight as shown by the sharp DTA exothermic peak at 960° with the formation of CoO. The complex $[\text{CoCl}(\text{acacN})(\text{py})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ loses the water molecule and one molecule of pyridine at 190–280° with a loss of 21.7% weight as evident from two sharp endothermic peaks on DTA curve. Thereafter it loses the second molecule of pyridine at 280–360° with a loss of 39.3% (38.6% theoretical). Then the compound loses 1/3rd. of the acetoacetanilide molecule (loss 52.7%) at 360–540° and then rest 2/3rd. of the acetoacetanilide along with chlorine atom at 540–960° with the formation of CoO. The compound $[\text{CoCl}(\text{acacN})\text{Q}]$ loses the quinoline molecule at 245–300° shown by the sharp exothermic peak at 250° with a loss of 32.14% (32.25% theoretical). Then it loses 1/3rd. of acetoacetanilide molecule at 360° as evident from the sharp endothermic peak with a loss of 46.3%. Then it loses 1/3rd. molecule of acetoacetanilide at

660° shown by the endothermic peak with a loss of 62.4% weight (61.7% theoretical). Then the compound starts losing its weight and at 880° it loses the rest 1/3rd. of acetoacetanilide along with the chlorine atom with a loss of 82.2% (81.9% theoretical) with the formation of CoO.

The copper complex $[\text{CuCl}(\text{acacN})(\gamma\text{-pic})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ loses the water molecule at 140° shown by the sharp exothermic peak on DTA curve with a loss of 3.8% weight. Then it loses one molecule of γ -picoline as evident from the small exothermic peak at 180° with a loss of 23.8% (24.5% theoretical). Thereafter it loses the second molecule of γ -picoline at 260–440° with a loss of 41.9%. Then the compound loses the acacN molecule along with chlorine atom at 440–660° with a loss of 84.9% with the formation of CuO, and subsequently a mass loss of 89.8% is observed at 660–780° with the formation of metallic copper shown by the sharp exothermic peak at 780° on the DTA curve.

Based upon analytical and conductance data four Zn^{II} complexes may be presumably four-coordinated having a tetrahedral geometry around the metal ions.

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